

Evaluating Leadership Style for Skill Development at the Processing Plant of a Ghanaian Mine

Author's Details:

James Obiri-Yeboah¹, Frederick Somuah Obeng² and Joy Ansu Yeboah³

¹Metallurgical Manager, Metallurgy Department, Akroma Gold Company Ghana Limited, Nkawkaw, Ghana. obirik@yahoo.co.uk ²Human Resource and Community Development Manager, Human Resource and Community Development Department, Akroma Gold Company Ghana Limited, Nkawkaw, Eastern Region, Ghana fredobeng1@gmail.com ³Human resource assistance, Human Resource Department of Redeemer Hospital, Tarkwa. Ghana

Abstract

The consequential adverse outcome of poor leadership style calls for this research, to identify the perception of leadership style at the Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company Limited. The study pointed out the prevailing leadership style as laissez faire with the highest percentage score flow by transactional leadership style while transformational leadership is perceived as the least style practiced by leaders of the Processing Plant. The multifactor leadership questionnaire was used in this assessment with total sample size of 80 employees as 100 % respondent's coverage during the research. The study portrays percentage scores of 18.35%, 17.45%, 17.78% and 18.08% for Contingent reward, Management by exception active, Management by exception passive and Laissez-faire leadership style components respectively. Furthermore, the research shows increasing respective order from the lowest score of 12.15 % for idealized attributes through individual consideration, followed by idealized behavior and inspirational motivation to 17.03 % score for intellectual stimulation leadership characters. The shortfalls enumerated by the study were passive evaluation set target and postmortem mode of handling operational activities. Leadership training in effective utilization of variations between actuals and set targets as control tools is the solution to overcome the shortfalls. The overall standard deviation for the three leadership style mean percentage scores is given as 3.54 %.

Keywords: Leadership Style, Skill Development

Introduction

Leadership style is the method and attitude of providing direction, implementing plans, and inspiring people. Generally, it includes the total configuration of explicit and implicit actions executed by leaders towards achievement of set goals (Clark, 2015). Cherry (2020), described leadership style as a frontrunner's characteristic behaviors when directing, motivating, guiding, and handling sets of people. These definitions refer to leadership style as a mode of exercising influence by a frontrunner on followers or subordinates toward a given goal. Chua, (2016), pointed out that, skills development is the process of identifying individuals' skill gaps and refining these skills. It is important because one's skills are in direct relation with one's ability to accomplish plans with success. That is skill development is the improvement in the ability of an individual for better performance in one's area of operation or endeavor. Hence, evaluating leadership style for skill development implies, identifying the frontrunner's characteristic behaviors when influencing followers or subordinates toward a given goal in order to enhance their ability of performing better in their areas of operations. Therefore, the framework of this research covers evaluation of employee perception of their leaders' style in achieving their given goals at the Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company limited, Ghana. By using Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) developed by Bass & Avolio (1997) to identify the needed reliable employees' perception of leadership style prevailing at processing plant of Akroma Gold Company limited. This is due to the fact that the questionnaire has shown internal consistency of the method and alternative methods through numerous testing and retesting. Authentically, Abualrub & Alghamdi (2012), a correlation was found between the multifactor leadership questionnaire (MLQ-5X) and the job satisfaction survey in which the result justifies the importance of transformational leadership.

Clearly, the current frequent and numerous subordinate and superior stalemates among employees of the Processing Plant, point to lacks of the needed leadership skill of the respective frontrunners. Consequently, this paper is to close the ineffective leadership skill gap existing in the company as a solution to eradicate the deadlock and institutional factionalism situations which have potency of destroying team work. The paper aims at identifying the various leadership styles of the supervisors and develops training programs to address the shortfall that exist in the different styles. The goal of the research is to enhance leadership skill development to foster team work as a recipe for excellence and profit maximization. That is, as per Metallurgical Report, (2019), this research is to enhance recovery of the quarter one (1) (i.e. quarte one (1) of 2020) production budget shortfall of 6% after the leadership skill development.

Background Information and Leadership style at the Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company Limited

Basically, this research is to enhance leadership skill development in order to ensure the existence of excellent team work to overcome the 6% budgetary shortfall of previous quarter (i.e. quarter one (1) of 2020). This study will help the company in developing management training to influence leadership skill which will lead to increase in productivity and profit maximization. The Process Plant of Akroma Gold Company Limited, Ghana, is represented diagrammatically as figure 1 and figure 2 shows the organizational structure.

Figure 1. Processing Plant Diagram of Akroma Gold Company Limited, Ghana (Haigen & Longzong, 1997)

From Figure 1, the sections of the plant are: the ROM (Run of Mine), Crusher, Grinding (Mill and Classification), Leaching, Desorption (Elution), Metal Recovery and Dry Tailing. Other sections are: Water setting Pond (Process water), Back Water poll, Fresh water (Raw Water), Water Dam, Fresh water poll and Well. Operationally, the Primary crusher is fed with 500mm ore from ROM and gives out product size of 128 to 130mm which then is fed into the secondary crusher to gain a product size of 12 to 22mm. The crushed product is screened to a product size of 12mm as mill feed. The primary mill feed size of 12mm is milled to 65% -74 μ m

after primary cyclone classification overflow product which is fed into the secondary mill. The secondary mill product is sent through secondary classification to obtain cyclone overflow product size of 95%-74µm as feed to the thickener. The 63.6m² thickeners feeds the two leaching tanks which subsequently feed the 8 Carbon-in-Leach tanks. Leaching is done at about 200ppm cyanide concentration at 10 to 11 pH level in 135m³ leach tanks at 39.08m³ per hour, with residence time of 24 to 32.92 hours. Carbon from the leaching tanks is sent for Zadra elution at loaded carbon level of 1500 to 2000g/t of carbon. Strip pregnant solution from the Zadra elution process is sent for electrowinning at a flow rate of 1.39l/s and duration of 16 to 24 hours, after which the cathodes are taken for smelting at 1250°C.

Innovatively, the Akroma Process Plant method is such that the treated tailings slurry is pumped into a dry tailings equipment instead of the usual tailing dam compartment. At the exit point of dry tailing equipment, the liquid is directed into settling pond while the solids are allowed to fall off from series of filter cloth, through the “under section” onto the concreted ground. The solids product of about 80% dry solids are then picked up by the use of loaders for onward other industrial usage as well as deposition for old mine pit reclamation (Haigen & Longzong, 1997)

Figure 2. Organizational Chart for Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company Limited, Ghana

Managerially, the Processing department of Akroma Gold Company limited has the organizational structure shown as figure 2 (Human resource Chart, 2017). Notably, figure 2 depicts the prevailing organogram captured a total of eighty (80) employees during the research work. The legend colour code describes the different category of employees as the head of department, superintendent, supervisor and operator with green, yellow, light blue and gray respectively. The organogram comprises of the one (1) metallurgical Manager (Head of department), three (3) superintendents, nine (9) supervisors and sixty seven (67) subordinates (i.e. operators and artisans). The metallurgical manager is the head of the day to day strategic focus of the Processing Plant. The superintendents of the various sections being managed include: production (i.e. crushing, milling and

extraction), Technical and engineering. Each superintendent controls three supervisors which are categorized into three shifts (i.e. Shift A, B and C). The three shift of technical section consists of research/development, data management and laboratory works (sample preparation, wet chemistry and sample analysis segments) while the engineering section is made up of mechanical (mech.), electrical (elect.), project and condition monitoring (pcm) groups.

The Superintendents are responsible for the day to day assessment and reporting of plant performance and critical shortfalls that need interventions to enhance the strategic focus of the plant by directing their respective supervisors. Specifically, the supervisors direct the day to day task of their respective subordinate towards the implementation of daily operations and measures to achieve the plant set target. Again, from figure 2, each of the production supervisors for shift A, B and C has a total of twelve (12) subordinates distributed to operate the crushing, milling, extraction and tailing segments under their leadership. The number of technical section subordinates for supervisors (Shift Metallurgist) of shift A, B and C have five (5) members each. The number of engineering section subordinates (Artisans) for supervisors of mechanical, electrical, project and condition monitoring are 6, 5, and 5 respectively. On the average, each supervisor has approximately seven subordinates (Operators/Artisans) under his or her leadership.

Technically, the Plant leadership is made up of the Head of department, Superintendents and the supervisors. The leadership characteristics of employees of these said positions cut across dictatorship, democratic, coaching, participating, and situational among others with their associated downside effects are perceived in all the sections of the department. The integrated nature of Processing Plant leadership skills call for the use of multifactor domain. Notably, as per Bass & Avolio, (1994), the Plant leaders display several leadership styles from transformational leadership to transactional leadership and even some rudiments of laissez-faire leadership style. That is, while some of the leaders are seen to have influence on individuals subordinates by inspiring workers to perform beyond expectations which is the transformational mode, others behave in the transactional leaders domain by making sure that fulfillment of expectations are met with rewards. Additionally, passive behaviors that are seen in the leaders at some instances can be categorized as lazier faire characters.

Largely, Vignettes, 2000, pointed out four leadership responsibilities which cover strategic or proactive persuasions, motivational inputs, creation of enterprise mission and building organizational culture as pivotal skills for all frontrunner characters. These functions require training to overcome their related shortfalls which have portray their ugly heads in order to release full benefits of the various leaders. Hence, the need to assess and provide training inputs to eradicate characteristic shortfalls to enhance leadership excellence at Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company limited, Ghana.

Material and Method used

Principally, skill deficits of the current leadership levels at Processing Plant of Akroma Gold Company limited, Ghana are recipes for production and revenue discrepancies. Therefore, the perceptions of subordinates about their respective leaders were studied through the use Avolio & Bass, (1997) multifactor leadership questionnaire to evaluate their respective strength and weakness. These strength and weakness serve as keys for generating training programs that can ensure leadership skill improvement. The multifactor leadership questionnaire (MLQ) measured perceptions of subordinates as transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership styles. The MLQ is distributed into leadership styles sectors as extra effort, effectiveness and satisfaction. The scale point values are 4, 3, 2, 1, 0 which relate to frequently or if not always, fairly often, sometimes, once a while and not at all respectively. Several investigators have established the reliability and consistency of the MLQ with internal consistency ranges from a Cronbach's alpha of 0.64 to 0.92 for 36-item (Avolio & Bass, 1994; Handsome, 2009). Respondents (i.e. subordinate employees per this study) are to select one scale point value for each question. Each leadership scale item scores are averaged. Higher scores on a

leadership style represent a stronger tendency towards that particular leadership style and lower score on a given the leadership style represent a lower tendency occurrence of that character leadership.

Quantitative evaluations of idealized attributes (IA), idealized behaviour (IB), inspirational motivation (IM), intellectual stimulation (IS) and individual consideration (IC) which correspond to transformational style of leaders and were obtained to enhance practical conclusions. This is a clear indication of leadership functions of trust building, acting with integrity, inspiring other, encouraging innovative thinking and coaching people. Again, transactional leadership style evaluation were from contingent reward (CR) (rewards achievement) and active management –by-exception (MBE -A) (i.e. mistake monitoring) leadership roles indications on the respondents questionnaire (i.e. MLQ). Furthermore, evaluations for passive management-by-exception (MBE -P) and avoids of involvement (LF- laissez faire) leadership style were scored as laissez faire characters (Bass & Avolio, 1994). Imperatively, Saunders et. al (2009), affirmed the use of bar chart options to limit of values of one or more independent variable. Clearly, from the research, evaluations of the factors of multifactor model and their corresponding percentage levels of leadership style scores were generated. These point to the use of statistical approach of bar chart as the appropriate model method for identifying the strength of the various leaders of the Processing Plant to enhance the drawing of leadership skill development program for the said sectional leaders at Akroma Gold Company Limited, Ghana.

Results and Discussions

Fundamentally, the insufficiency of information on the leadership style in the Akroma Gold Company Limited and its interrelated potential destruction of teamwork as well as its detrimental effect on skill development are the gaps that this study seeks to examine. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to close the information gaps in the existing company situation to enhance the appropriate leadership style for skill development.

Analytically, the organizational structure, demographic data and statistical data on the bases of how each data relates to the research focus was done. Demographic statistics evaluation of respondents includes: organizational structure position, gender, age and number of years in the current company. Table 1 and Figure 1 show the total of 80 workers and the company's chain of command positions which comprise of unit manager, superintendents, supervisors and subordinates with percentage of response as 1.3 %, 3.8 %, 11.3 % and 83.8 % respectively. Out of the 80 participant in the study, 80 % were male and 20 % female as shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. Evidently, the industry is male dominated enterprise. Departmental composition of respondents consists of 25 % engineering, 24 % Technical and 51 % Production of the overall 80 participants as shown in Table 3 and Figure 3. In terms of age the distribution shows that 18 % of the participants were below 20 years (yrs), 56 % were between 21 – 30 years, 19 % were between 31- 40 years, 5 % were between 41 – 50 years and 3 % were above 50 years as shown in Table 4 and Figure 4. The distribution of employee years of work in the company consist of 49 % , 29 %, 9 %, 8 % and 6 % for years of 1 – 5, 6 – 10, 11 – 15, 16 – 20 and above 20 years(yrs) respectively as shown in Table 5 and Figure 5. The 49 % of the work force with between 1 to 5 years work experience, depict that a high number of the workers are inexperience which implies leadership coaching will be required to enhance conducive atmosphere for improvement.

Table 1. Organizational structure composition of position

Position	Expected Outcome	Number of responses	Variance	% of response
Unit Manager	1	1	0	1.3
Superintendents	3	3	0	3.8
Supervisors	9	9	0	11.3
Subordinates	67	67	0	83.8
Total	80	80	0	100

Figure 1. Chart of Organizational structure composition of position

Table 2. Respondents gender composition

GENDER	No. of responses	% of response
Male	64	80
Female	16	20
Total	80	100

Figure 2. Respondents gender composition

Table 3. Respondents' departmental composition

DEPARTMENT	No. of responses	% of response
Engineering	20	25
Technical	19	24
Production	40	51
Total	79	100

Figure 3. Chart of Respondents’ departmental composition

Table 4. Respondents’ age composition

AGE	No. of responses	% of response
Below 20years	14	18
21-30years	45	56
31-40years	15	19
41-50years	4	5
50+ years	2	3
Total	80	100

Figure 4. Respondents’ age composition graph

Table 5. Respondents’ length of service

LENGTH OF SERVICE	No. of responses	% of response
0-5 yrs	39	49
6-10yrs	23	29
11-15yrs	7	9
16-20yrs	6	8
20+ yrs	5	6

Figure 5. Respondents' length of service graph

From the multifactor leadership questionnaire, average responses scored by each leadership style scale were obtained. Rating ranged from 0 to 4 for each response. The transformational leadership scale components of the multifactor leadership questionnaire are: idealized attributes, idealized behaviors, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. These components of transformational leadership style questions on the multifactor leadership questionnaire correspond to item numbers of 2, 6, 8, 10, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 29, 30, 31, 32, 34 and 36. Similarly, transactional leadership style scale on the multifactor leadership questionnaire consist of contingent reward and management by exception active. The related item numbers for transactional leadership style are 1, 4, 11, 16, 22, 24, 27 and 35. Additionally, the scale for laissez-faire leadership comprising of laissez-faire leadership and management by exception passive relate to the item numbers of 3, 5, 7, 12, 17, 20 and 28.

From table 6 and figure 6, leaders and subordinates with total sample number (n) of 80, illustrated idealized attributes (IA) having a mean percentage score of 12.15 % Idealized behavior (IB) had a mean percentage score of 14.65 %. Inspirational motivation (IM) had a mean percentage score of 15.88 %. Intellectual stimulation (IS) had a mean percentage score of 17.03 % Individual consideration (IC) had a mean percentage score of 14.93 %. Contingent reward (CR) had a mean percentage score of 18.35 %. Management by exception active (MBEA) had a mean percentage score of 17.45 %. Management by exception passive (MBEP) had a mean percentage score of 17.78 %. Laissez-faire leadership (LF) had a mean percentage score of 18.03 %. The overall standard deviation of 2.04 % for the mean percentage scores

Table 6. MQL overall results.

Leadership style		Subordinate	Leaders	Mean of Averages Scores
		Average score	Average score	
Transformational	IA	19.11	5.2	12.15
	IB	25.4	3.9	14.65
	IM	25.6	6.15	15.88
	IS	27.15	6.9	17.03
	IC	24.55	5.3	14.93
Transactional	CR	29.6	7.1	18.35
	MBE-A	29.05	5.85	17.45
Laissez faire	MBE-P	28.65	6.9	17.78
	LF	29.1	6.95	18.03
Total		238.21	54.25	146.23

Figure 6. MQL overall results.

The high percentage scores of 18.35%, 17.45%, 17.78% and 18.08% portray on figure 6 for Contingent reward (CR), Management by exception active (MBEA), Management by exception passive (MBEP) and Laissez-faire respectively, depict leadership that rewards achievement, monitors mistake, engages in passive evaluation set target and avoids involvement in the daily issues of employees' welfare. Notably, rewarding achievement is character that gives encouragement for hard work among employees on one hand. On the other hand these characters have negative connotations that point to lack of employees' self-motivation, absence of proactive supervision, lack of effective supervisory control and coaching from the plant leadership. Again, figure 6, shows an increasing respective order from the lowest score of 12.15 % for idealized attributes (IA) through individual consideration (IC), follow by idealized behavior (IB) and inspirational motivation (IM) to 17.03 % score for intellectual stimulation (IS) leadership characters

Table 7 and figure 7 depict the leaders and subordinates mean percentage scores for the three leadership styles (transformational, transactional and laissez-faire). Laissez-faire leadership was highly rated within the sample with mean percentage score of 35.82 % out of the 80 samples of respondents. Transactional leadership had mean percentage score of 34.90 % out of the 80 sample of respondents. Transformational leadership had a mean percentage score of 29.28 %. The overall standard deviation for the three leadership style mean percentage scores was evaluated as 3.54 %.

Table 7. Leadership style results

Leadership style	Leaders Percentage Score	Subordinates Percentage Score	Mean Percentage Score
Transformational	29.1	29.5	29.28
Transactional	34.3	35.5	34.90
Laissez faire	36.7	35.0	35.82

Figure 7. Leadership style results.

From figure 7, laissez-faire leadership is the highest perceived leadership style mean score followed by transactional leadership with the transformational leadership being the lowest score at the Process Plant of Akroma Company Limited. Notably, Chaudhry & Javed, (2012), portrayed that, laissez-faire leadership of the section relinquishes tasks and eludes making decisions. That is, leaders of this leadership style, show their passive nature by waiting to take action only when a mistake is brought to their attention. These types of leaders permit subordinates to work in their own way and take responsibility for their acts and inactions. Clearly, this gives an indication of low motivational levels and high passive management character as a result of lack of management interference associated with its practice. This type of leadership style always takes decisions in the postmortem mode of attitude towards feedbacks or support to follower. Again, figure 7 shows that, Transactional leadership is perceived as the second highest prevailing leadership style as compared to laissez-faire leadership and transformational leadership style at the Process Plant of Akroma Company Limited. DuBrin, (2010) pointed out that, transactional leadership is based on the social learning and social exchange theories which recognize the reciprocal nature of leadership. Thus, transactional leader focuses on more schedule transactions, rewarding group members for meeting standards. However, the major downside of transactional leaders portrayed by the writers is its potential of building a group that lack innovation and sacrifice for better future organizational development.

Furthermore, figure 7 portrays transformational leadership as the lowest leadership style prevailing at the Process Plant of Akroma Company Limited. Imperatively, transformational leadership is considered by DuBrin (2010) as the leadership style that brings about positive developments in an organization. The writer pointed out that a transformational leader focuses on activities through a good relationship with group members. Hence, transformational leaders are charismatic, extraverted, visionaries, encourage personal development of the staff and give supportive leadership. Agreeably, there are positive associations between transformational leadership style and organizational development but its potential adverse effect of overlooking individual behavioral weakness under the pretext of building good relationship deserves attention. Resultantly, the below 40% perception score for all the three leadership styles call for acritical attention on the detrimental characteristics of the different leadership styles prevailing in the section under this research consideration.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Profoundly, the inadequacy of information on the leadership style in the Akroma Gold Company Limited and its prospective downward effect on teamwork as well as skill development are the gaps that this study seeks to bring out. Consequently, this study is to close the information gaps in the existing company's Processing Plant on the subject of the leadership style for skill development. The scores of 35.82%, 34.90% and 29.28% for laissez-faire, transactional and transformational leadership styles respectively, call for acritical attention on the detrimental characteristics of the different leadership styles to enhance skill development. The downward characteristics of three leadership styles noted in this study are low motivational levels, high passive management character, lack innovation, sacrifice for better future organizational development and adverse effect of neglecting individual behavioral weakness under the pretext of building good relationship. The high scores 18.35%, 17.45%, 17.78% and 18.08% for Contingent reward, Management by exception active, Management by exception passive and Laissez-faire respectively, depict leadership that lacks effective proactive skills. That is the leadership of the Processing Plant is highly skewed towards rewarding achievement, monitoring mistake, engaging in passive evaluation set target which are all reactive and postmortem mode of handling operational activities. Therefore, leadership training in innovational skills, motivational skills and effective utilization of variance analysis for set targets as control tools will go a long way to enhance maximization of productivity and performance. The 49 % of the work force with between 1 to 5 years work experience, depict that a high number of the workers are inexperienced which implies leadership coaching will be required to enhance conducive atmosphere for improvement. Recommendably, further research work on the relationship between the leadership style and productivity of will also enhance the need for change in the leadership attitude towards the betterment of the company.

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